

Reflections On Climate Action as Therapy: How I Got to The End of My Rope and Climbed Back Up

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ABSTRACT

The climate emergency demands urgent action to reduce emissions. Meanwhile, people around the world are experiencing the ravages of climate impacts, and all indications are that these impacts will continue to increase. The United Nations continues to remind us that many governments are not responding quickly enough to reduce emissions and future impacts. The magnitude of the problem and inadequate response is a mental burden to many. This commentary argues that climate action, including but not limited to non-violent civil disobedience may help to reduce this mental health burden.

Keywords: *Climate Action; Ethics; Collective Action*

PERSPECTIVE

Introduction

As a physician-scientist working on the health impacts of climate change I found myself in an uncomfortable position when, in 2014, my country approved a new pipeline from the Alberta Oilsands under my university and to a neighbouring tidewater terminal in Vancouver. My expertise in epidemiology and toxicology was called upon for several reports about the health impacts of the project that can be anticipated based upon previous events and the infrastructure and technology in the proposed pipeline expansion project. Remarkably, when preparing and writing my reports to the government I was told that the climate-related health impacts would not be considered. This critical factor was removed by the government of then Prime Minister Stephen Harper, who -- not coincidentally is from Alberta, the Canadian province with the largest oil and gas sector in the country. Despite the stacked deck, four years later, support for the project dwindled to such an extent that the Texas pipeline giant, Kinder Morgan considered it too risky to continue and walked away from the

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project. The pipeline project was then 'saved' by the Liberal government of the day under Justin Trudeau, with the justification that all proceeds would go to fund Canada's climate action (CBC 2021). After my reports (Takaro, et al, 2015; Takaro et al, 2018) and a resolution by the Health Officers' Council of BC demanding an "independent, cumulative and comprehensive health impacts assessment" were ignored (HOC 2019), I got to the end of my rope. I knew that evidence was not going to be sufficient in the arguments against the project, and in August 2020 I found myself camped up in a tree blocking construction, and I founded a direct-action group called Protect the Planet. Our non-violent direct-action blockade went on for an additional sixteen months (CBC 2020).

This commentary focusses on climate action in the context of mental health and includes:

- (1) a discussion of what mental health related obligations Public Health has in the climate emergency;
- (2) exploration of an ethics framework for climate action in public health;
- (3) consideration of the role of non-violent civil disobedience in climate action;
- (4) an argument that taking action can be individually and collectively therapeutic, and
- (5) an examination of some legal tools available to force more timely action on climate change.

Mental health and the climate emergency

It is not surprising that more and more people are reporting distress, anxiety and depression related to the climate crisis. It is clearly an existential threat (Guterres, 2018) that governments like Canada -- who continue to build large new fossil energy infrastructure -- are not addressing seriously enough (IPCC 2023). The fossil energy industry has known since the 1970s that their emissions could cause the current crisis, and instead of acting to reduce emissions, they pursued a disinformation campaign and attempted to shift blame to individual behavior, adding to the pathology (Hickman et al, 2021; Supran et al, 2023). The psychiatric literature describes this category of environmental distress reactions as psychoterratic syndromes that include ecoanxiety, solastalgia (distress caused by loss or degradation of a cherished environment) and ecoparalysis (apathy or limbo due to ecoanxiety) (Cianconi, et al, 2023). They are frequently linked to clinical depression and anxiety as discussed by other papers in this journal. Considering the existential nature of the threat, these responses may be considered a normal reaction to a dire situation. Well-designed actions to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions and build community resilience to climate threats such as active transportation, environmental stewardship, increasing green infrastructure and enhanced social networks can also benefit mental health (Health Canada 2022), so there is a strong rationale for examining therapeutic options for these syndromes.

The evidence that taking action on climate change is therapeutic for eco-anxiety is circumstantial at best. Clearly research is needed to examine whether such action is indeed therapeutic and for whom it is effective. Further, we need to learn what are the most effective actions and how we might intervene to enhance their use if found to be therapeutic. Research in this area requires an understanding of how trauma and stress affects physiology and the mind (McEwen 2012). Therefore, developing modes to increase social support networks, find new meaning and purpose in life and learn methods for calming and focus are all important skills to test for effectiveness for eco-anxiety.

Many mental health professionals support the idea that taking action on climate is effective in the management of depression and anxiety due to climate change. The American Psychiatry Association has issued a recent statement that, "The most effective method to reduce anxiety and depression and sustain hope in the face of the climate crisis is to engage in purposeful action within one's community and take individual action. The latter includes reducing fossil fuel use, making homes more energy efficient, and shifting to diets that are more plant based." (Feder 2022). Recognizing and calling out the

complicity of fossil energy companies may also be therapeutic. I will briefly describe my own climate actions over the past several years to stop a large fossil energy project, the Transmountain Pipeline Expansion Project (TMX) and how I used them to maintain my own mental health.

An ethics framework for climate action

This pipeline was authorized by the Canadian Cabinet the day after Parliament declared a national climate emergency. As noted above, I was an active participant in the government review of the project, leading a research team that produced two extensive reports on the health impacts of the project, but we were forbidden from bringing the climate impacts into these reports. That and our other, reported concerns were not addressed. After my years of research on the health impacts of the project and the ignored request to government from the Health Officers' Council of BC, it was clear that the evidence of harm would not stop TMX. Emissions continued to rise despite promises made by Canada to reduce them (Gov. Canada 2015), especially in the oil and gas sector (Gov. Canada 2022).

As a physician I took an oath to protect the health of people, including a duty-to-care, to “accept a share of the profession’s responsibility to society in matters relating to public health, health education, environmental protection, and legislation affecting the health or well-being of the community...” (CMA 1996). Even the relatively conservative American Medical Association is explicit about a physician’s ethical duties and the law, “ethical responsibilities usually exceed legal duties...[W]hen physicians believe a law violates ethical values or is unjust they should work to change the law. In exceptional circumstances of unjust laws, ethical responsibilities should supersede legal duties,” (AMA 2016).

The role of non-violent civil disobedience

In this case, it was clear that evidence would not sway Government on the project, and all other avenues for dissent had been ignored, so non-violent civil disobedience (NVCD) was the only remaining option for protecting the planet and my patients. After fulfilling the criteria for NVCD as outlined in *The Lancet* (Bennet et al, 2019, See **Table 1**), I drew upon experience in the civil rights movement of my birth country (USA) and a lifetime of mountaineering experience, to block the project with my body, high in the trees in my hometown, trees that would need to be cut for the new pipeline. The tree-sit became a rallying point for others frustrated by government inaction on climate change and we were able to block the project over 16 months in different trees along the route. Eventually, many of us went to jail with sentences up to 60 days.

NVCD is an effective way to bring about societal change. The IPCC concludes with ‘high confidence’ that collective action connected to social movements plays a substantial role pressuring governments to create new laws and policy for carbon emissions (IPCC 2022). Meta-analysis of social movements contesting fossil energy projects show non-violent civil disobedience (NVCD) contributes to success over and above other tactics such as petitions, letters-to-the-editors or elected representatives (Thiri et al, 2022), all of which were widely used in the early periods of the campaign to stop TMX before hundreds resorted to NVCD.

Table 1. Criteria That Can Help Justify Non-Violent Civil Disobedience

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- Situation is unjust
 - NVCD is the last resort
 - NVCD is more effective than harmful
 - NVCD is the least harmful action
 - Sociopolitical situation is considered
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Note: Adapted from Bennet et al. (2020)

Taking action can be individually and collectively therapeutic

For me, the direct action on climate change in the fight against TMX has been very therapeutic. In the years leading up to the COVID-19 pandemic, the reports from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and other evidence-based bodies examining the response of earth systems to global heating, grew increasingly dire. I was a lead author on one of these, *Health of Canadians in a Changing Climate: Advancing our Knowledge for Action* (Health Canada, 2022). My team worked on the water security chapter. Water is critical for life, and yet we are failing to prepare adequately for the climate future with water quality and quantity threats that are already apparent. Some Indigenous and other rural communities still live without clean water. Stage five water restrictions (the highest level) are becoming more common in the west, and drought destabilizes politically volatile parts of the planet (Health Canada 2022).

This dark picture was emerging prior to the pandemic that shook the globe in spring of 2020. Alberta's Energy Minister, Sonia Savage noted, "Now is a great time to be building a pipeline because you can't have protests of more than 15 people". "Let's get it [TMX] built." (CBC 2020a). Yet we in Protect the Planet were strong and stood tall in the trees in Burnaby and with help from hummingbirds and other protected species whose nesting periods stopped construction, were able to maintain blockades and camps for 16 months, with hundreds of people, while keeping safe with COVID-19 protocols. We all benefited from the community spirit and focus on a common goal.

Well planned climate action can lead to opportunities to improve health, equity, and human rights. It provides agency for people previously disempowered. We found that purposeful action with our community, both individual and collective action, was an effective method to reduce anxiety and depression and sustain hope in the face of the climate crisis. We were boosted by the public attention brought to the project. This illumination and the support from colleagues and friends made the dark period easier.

Legal tools available to force more timely climate action

Civil disobedience is public, nonviolent action in breach of the law, which is aimed at changing the law or policies of the government. Such action is an act of conscience, and participants accept possible punishment. It is effective (IPCC, 2022), but sitting in a tree and being arrested is not everyone's calling. We all have gifts to bring to the climate crisis. We can all take actions and these actions vary between individuals and over time. Ayana Elizabeth Johnson provides a useful approach to understanding how one can personally realize effective climate action in **Figure 1** (Johnson AE, 2021).

Finding your place along the spectrum of possible actions may prove therapeutic for you too. I am not Indigenous, but in this struggle I have benefited much from the Indigenous knowledge of my fellow land-defenders who are. Canada has committed itself to the Declaration of the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (DRIPA). They made me ask, what would it mean to realize DRIPA in Canada? The First Peoples on this land made a contract with the salmon thousands of years ago. They would care for the streams, rivers, oceans, trees and all those things that connect, show gratitude and humility in the face of the abundance all around them, and in return the salmon would allow themselves to be fished at the same time every year. The heads and bones are ceremoniously returned to the waters in thanks. It is a reciprocal relationship. Their technology of fish weirs and traps would have permitted them to take many more fish each run, but they did not. In 175 years, the settlers on these lands have nearly wiped out the salmon. We must learn from those who successfully stewarded the land since time-out-of-mind. We have a responsibility to future generations to do this learning, and this is, in part, what DRIPA means.

Figure 1. Ready to take action? Find this sweet spot.

In its reports the UN Intergovernmental Panel on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services notes that nature is declining less rapidly in Indigenous peoples' land than in other lands. They show that Indigenous governance and customary institution and management regimes that involve Indigenous peoples' and local communities can be an effective way to safeguard nature (IPBES 2019). Indigenous knowledge could lead us out of the moral quandary that we have found ourselves in here in Canada, the quandary where we know it is not right to build new infrastructure locking in future emissions, but we are somehow convinced our increased oil and gas production are justified. Indigenous teachings guide us in our work on the unceded territories of the Coast Salish Peoples here in British Columbia. Here are some additional ways you might take action to collectively reduce emissions:

- Legally, compel industries to account for costs of operations to the planet and future generations, building on Dutch success in their supreme court (*Urgenda Foundation v. State of the Netherlands* 2015).
- Work with your elected representatives to expand taxation on carbon to include social and health costs of carbon emissions (Rennert et al. 2022).
- Join the Sue Big Oil campaign (grown in British Columbia) (West Coast Env. Law 2022).
- Advance stronger fossil emission reduction legislation, e.g. Green New Deal bill M-1 (Sponsored by MP Peter Julian in Canada 2020)
- Defend future generations using human rights tribunals, e.g. Philippines HR Commission. (Amnesty International 2019)
- Get your municipality to adopt the Fossil Fuel Non-proliferation Treaty (Fossil Fuel Treaty Initiative 2019)
- Follow the money and push fossil energy divestment– U.S. and Canadian banks are major financiers of fossil energy projects worldwide (e.g. RBC \$9.2 B, JP Morgan Chase \$51.3 B in past year, 2021-22) (Banking on Climate Chaos 2022). Change to a credit union that invests more ethically than big banks.
- Expose the insurers of fossil projects and risks (18 have dropped Trans Mountain pipeline to date; Stand.earth 2022).

- Block new Canadian fossil energy infrastructure with your body (Protect the Planet 2023).
- Through your family, friends and organizations where you have influence, help realize the Declaration on Rights of Indigenous Peoples (DRIPA) and its inherent protection of the planet (BC Gov 2019)

CONCLUSION

We are in a pandemic of denial on the urgency of the climate emergency, but this denial is treatable. The treatment is education and action. The time for this is now. Where you are at in this moment is the place. Not everyone is inclined to NVCD, but everyone has their gifts to bring to the broad action agenda outlined here. You are one of many voices for change and by taking action, in your own personal way, you can find hope for the future as we all navigate collectively through the climate emergency.

DECLARATIONS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Without my supportive family and the many volunteers in Protect the Planet and other organizations we work with, this journey would not have been possible.

FUNDING

None.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

Not applicable.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Not applicable.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Not applicable.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The Authors declare they have no competing interests.

PUBLICATION DATES

Received: 3 April 2023

Accepted: 05 September 2023

Published: 01 October 2023

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